

**Spectrophotometric Estimation of Naturally
occurring Volatile Constituents of
Antimicrobial Oils**

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THE plants *A. indica*¹ and *Majorana hortensis*² belong to natural order Labiatae and *Eupatorium triplinerve*³ belongs to natural order Compositae. Essential oils of the plants are useful in many diseases^{4,5}. We have found that essential oils of all the plants possess good antimicrobial activity⁶. In view of this, further investigation has been carried out for the quantitative estimation of some of the components spectrophotometrically.

Essential oils from the leaves of *A. indica*, *M. hortensis* and *E. triplinerve* (obtained from United Chemicals & Allied Products, Calcutta) were isolated by steam distillation method using

Clevenger's apparatus. Physicochemical data of essential oil of these plants are compiled in Table 1.

TABLE 1—PHYSICO-CHEMICAL DATA OF ESSENTIAL OILS OF PLANTS*

Sl. no.	Parameter	<i>M.h</i>	<i>A.i</i>	<i>E.t</i>
1.	Sp. gravity	0.845 (at 33°)	0.911 (at 35°)	0.786 (at 36°)
2.	Phenol content	48.00	47.50	41.50
3.	Refractive index at 14.5°	1.5060	1.5070	1.5101
4.	Optical rotation	+40.30°	-4 to +8°	+39.10°
5.	Acid value	5.6	5.4	5.00
6.	Ester value	38.00	37.00	36.00
7.	Ester value ^a	44.26	44.27	43.86

M.h=*M. hortensis*, *A.i*=*A. indica*, *E.t*=*E. triplinerve*.
^aEster value after acetylation.

Colour reaction and spectrophotometric estimation method are given below.

α-Terpineol: The essential oils of leaves of *M. hortensis* (1.2 g) and *A. indica* (1.8 g) were taken separately in 80% alcohol and each solution was made up to 20 ml and then vanillin hydrochloric acid reagent (1% solution of vanillin in concentrated hydrochloric acid) was added, heated to 50° to get a bluish violet colour and the respective optical densities were noted at 246 mμ.

Eugenol: The essential oils of leaves of *M. hortensis* (2.0 g) and leaves of *A. indica* (1.4 g) were taken separately and each solution was made upto 20 ml with absolute alcohol, and then a 20% alcoholic ferric chloride reagent (4-5 drops) was added and the respective optical densities were noted at 260 mμ.

Citral: To the essential oil of leaves of *A. indica* (1.5 g) taken in the test tube and the volume (10 ml), made up in glacial acetic acid was added E.M. reagent⁷ (2 ml; the reagent being a mixture of solutions of a 5% *p*-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde in acetic acid and a 10% phosphoric acid in acetic acid) and the optical density of pink colour was noted at 280 mμ.

1,8-Cineole: To each of the essential oils of leaves of *M. hortensis*, *A. india* (2.0 g) and *E. triplinerve* (1.5 g) taken in absolute alcohol (15 ml), was added freshly prepared Schorn's reagents⁸ (a mixture of 10 ml of 30% ammonium molybdate solution, 10 ml of concentrated nitric acid and 20 ml of 5% ammonium sulphate solution) and the respective optical density of blue coloured solutions was noted at 274 mμ.

Limonene: To different amounts of each of the essential oil of leaves of *M. hortensis* and *A. indica* taken in glacial acetic acid (20 ml), was added saturated solution (2 ml) of picric acid in glacial acetic acid and heated for 8-10 min, and the respective optical density of the red coloured solutions was noted at 250 mμ.

Percentage of each of the five components was calculated with the help of their respective

calibration curve drawn between the optical density and concentration of the pure components. The results of colourimetric estimation (Table 2) have been found to be in conformity with those of glc analysis. Hence, spectrophotometric estimations may potentially be successfully exploited for estimating and in effect formulating important antimicrobial preparations.

TABLE 2—SPECTROPHOTOMETRIC ESTIMATION OF VOLATILE CONSTITUENTS*

Sl. no.	Plant**	α-Terpi- neol %	Euge- nol %	Citral %	1,8-Cineole %	Limo- nene %
1.	<i>M.h</i>	4.90 (4.80)	25.50 (26.00)	—	7.50 (7.32)	2.40 (2.94)
2.	<i>A.i</i>	3.00 (2.10)	25.00 (24.50)	10.00 (9.50)	12.00 (11.90)	2.80 (3.00)
3.	<i>E.t</i>	—	—	—	8.00 (7.92)	—

*Figures in paranthesis are by glc analysis.

**Abbreviation of the plants same as in Table 1.

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References

1. R. N. CHOPRA, S. L. NAYAR and I. C. CHOPRA, "Glossary of Indian Medicinal Plants", C. S. I. R., New Delhi, 1956, p. 19.
2. Ref. 1, p. 160.
3. Ref. 1, p. 113.
4. "Wealth of India Raw Materials", C. S. I. R., New Delhi, 1948, Vol. I, p. 79; 1962, Vol. VI, p. 227.
5. K. R. KIRTIKAR and B. D. BASU, *Indian Medicinal plants*, Lalit Mohan, Allahabad, 1935, 1, 1333.
6. R. N. YADAV and V. K. SAINI, *Indian Perfumer*, 1990, 34, 61; 1991, 35, 58.
7. ARNO-MULLER, *J. Parvkt. Chem.*, 1938, 151, 233.
8. SCHORN, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1935, 19, 7574.